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CONSIDERING THE APPLICATION OF THE EU PIL SYSTEM TO CLIMATE CHANGE LITIGATION

Abstract: *Climate change has progressively emerged as a critical global concern, involving various sectors and stakeholders. Internationally, both soft law guiding principles and hard law legislative instruments like the Kyoto Protocol and the Paris Agreement address climate change impacts. Within the EU, climate change goals are pursued through initiatives such as the European Green Deal, the European Climate Change Law and the Fit-for-55 Package. This regulatory backdrop imposes specific obligations on states and entities to mitigate climate change effects and invest sustainably, while impacting commercial contracts across various industries. The interplay between natural climate phenomena coexisting with human activities leads to potential disputes regarding environmental laws or contractual violations related to climate issues at national and international levels. This necessitates an important role for private international law. The paper discusses the typology of disputes related to climate change, including the prerequisites for applying the EU PIL, and the rules regarding jurisdiction and applicable law in this context. It highlights the complex and fragmented nature of the current EU PIL system concerning jurisdiction and applicable law, as it pertains to the specific case, resulting in both forum shopping and qualification shopping practices.*

Keywords: *Climate change litigation, dispute resolution, EU PIL, jurisdiction, applicable law.*

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1. Introduction

According to the IPCC Report 2023, human activities, primarily through GHG emissions, have clearly led to global warming, resulting in a global surface temperature increase of 1.1°C above pre-industrial levels in the period 2011–2020. There has been a continual rise in global GHG emissions, with disparities in historical and current contributions stemming from unsustainable energy usage, land use changes, and individual consumption patterns¹. The substantial effects of climate change have prompted discussions on its origins, consequences, and possible solutions.

At international level, soft law guiding principles and recommendations² have been accompanied by hard law legislative instruments to confront climate change impact. The Kyoto Protocol³, an international treaty extending the 1992 UNFCCC,⁴ was adopted at COP3 on 11 December 1997 and entered into force on 16 February 2005. It operationalised the UNFCCC by committing industrialised countries and economies in transition to limit and reduce GHG emissions in line with agreed individual objectives. Subsequently, another international treaty on climate change, the Paris Agreement⁵, was adopted at COP24 on 12 December 2015 and entered into force on 4 November 2016. Its overarching goal is to hold “the increase in the global average temperature to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels” and pursue efforts “to limit the temperature increase to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels”, which requires global GHG emissions to halve during the decade to

¹Lee, H., Romero, J. (eds), *IPCC Climate Change 2023: Synthesis Report – Contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*, Geneva, 2023, p. 4. Retrieved May 20, 2024, from <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/syr/>.

²E.g., OECD Guidelines for Multinational Enterprises 2011 Edition. Retrieved May 20, 2024, from <https://www.oecd.org/daf/inv/mne/48004323.pdf>; UN Human Rights Council Resolution (A/HRC/RES/17/4) of 16 June 2011 “Guiding Principles on Businesses and Human Rights”. Retrieved May 20, 2024, from https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/documents/publications/guidingprinciplesbusinessshr_en.pdf; UN General Assembly Resolution (A/RES/70/1) of 25 September 2015 “Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development”. Retrieved May 20, 2024, from https://www.un.org/en/development/desa/population/migration/generalassembly/docs/globalcompact/A_RES_70_1_E.pdf.

³Kyoto Protocol to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. Retrieved May 20, 2024, from <https://unfccc.int/resource/docs/convkp/kpeng.pdf>.

⁴United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (“UNFCCC”). Retrieved May 20, 2024, from https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/convention_text_with_annexes_english_for_posting.pdf.

⁵Paris Agreement. Retrieved May 20, 2024, from https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/english_paris_agreement.pdf.

2030 and CO² emissions to reach net zero by 2050 to restrain climate change. At EU level, climate change targets are currently pursued through the European Green Deal,⁶ the European Climate Change Law⁷ and the relevant Fit-for-55 Package.⁸

Due to the regulations mentioned above, states, public entities and private entities are now required to fulfil certain obligations in order to protect the environment and address climate change through adaptation and mitigation efforts.⁹ Many countries have implemented national climate laws and regulations that impact various activities with environmental implications,¹⁰ leading to a considerable rise in sustainable investments.¹¹

In this context, natural climate phenomena, human activities affecting climate, violations of environmental laws and climate regulations as well as breaches of contracts can lead to various climate change disputes. The rise in climate change disputes in recent years has consequently sparked more conversations about dispute resolution issues.

Bearing this in mind, this paper aims to highlight the fragmentation and complexity of the EU PIL rules on jurisdiction and applicable law to climate change litigation when the forum is an EU Member State, allowing both forum shopping and qualification shopping practices. After this introduction (1.), the typology of climate change related disputes and their interplay with EU PIL will be discussed (2.) and an overview of the applicable EU PIL rules on jurisdiction and applicable law will be provided (3.), ending with some conclusions of the author (4.).

⁶ Retrieved May 20, 2024, from https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en.

⁷ Regulation (EU) 2021/1119 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 June 2021 establishing the framework for achieving climate neutrality and amending Regulations (EC) No 401/2009 and (EU) 2018/1999 ('European Climate Law'), OJ L 243, 9.7.2021, 1–17.

⁸ Retrieved May 20, 2024, from https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/delivering-european-green-deal/fit-55-delivering-proposals_en.

⁹ See in general Lackner, M., Sajjadi, B., Chen, W.-Y. (eds), *Handbook of Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation* (3rd ed.), Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland AG, 2022, passim; Welfens, P., *Global Climate Change Policy. Analysis, Economic Efficiency Issues and International Cooperation*, Sustainable Development Goals Series 13, Cham: Palgrave Macmillan & Springer Nature Switzerland AG, 2022, passim.

¹⁰ E.g., the Greek National Climate Law no. 4936/2022 (Government Gazette A 105). See also LSE Grantham Research Institute on Climate Change and the Environment, *Climate Change Laws of the World*. Retrieved May 20, 2024, from <https://climate-laws.org/>.

¹¹ See GSIA, *Global Sustainable Investment Review 2020*. Retrieved May 20, 2024, from <https://www.gsi-alliance.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/GSIR-20201.pdf>.

2. Typology of climate change related disputes¹²

2.1. Definition of climate change related disputes

So far, there is no universal definition in legal texts or doctrine as to what may constitute a climate change related dispute. The following definitions can indicatively be considered as helping delineate the scope of such disputes:

The UNFCCC defines climate change as “[t]he change of climate which is attributed directly or indirectly to human activity that alters the composition of the global atmosphere and which is in addition to natural climate variability observed over comparable time periods”.

Based on the UNEP Global Climate Litigation Report 2020,¹³ climate change related cases can be considered those that relate specifically to climate change mitigation, adaptation, or the science of climate change.

The ICC Report on Resolving Climate Change Related Disputes through Arbitration and ADR 2019¹⁴ offers a broad description of climate change related disputes including “any dispute arising out of or in relation to the effect of climate change and climate change policy, the [...] UNFCCC and the Paris Agreement”.

2.2. Categories of climate change related disputes

Despite dealing with the same issue, i.e., climate change, climate change related disputes are not homogenous, but they significantly vary. They can be broadly divided into the following general and special categories:

2.2.1. General categories

According to their aims, climate change related disputes can be divided into two main categories:

¹²Sub-chapters 2.1. and 2.2. of this paper depict the definition and the categories of climate change related disputes, as referred to by the author in her article Koumpli, V., *Climate change related disputes: Making the case for arbitration and mediation*, Yearbook of International Arbitration & ADR – Volume VIII (eds M. Roth, M. Geistlinger), Zurich/Vienna: Dike Verlag AG & NWV Verlag GmbH, 2024, pp. 50-53 [forthcoming].

¹³UNEP, *Global Climate Litigation Report: 2020 Status Report*, p. 7. Retrieved May 20, 2024, from <https://wedocs.unep.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.11822/34818/GCLR.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>.

¹⁴ICC Commission on Arbitration and ADR, *Report on Resolving Climate Change Related Disputes through Arbitration and ADR*, 2019, p. 9. Retrieved May 20, 2024, from <https://iccwbo.org/climate-change-disputes-report>.

‘Strategic’ climate change related disputes, where the parties bringing the case – usually NGOs and/or individuals – aim at a broad societal shift, such as creating awareness or affecting the behaviour of states, public entities or private entities, including ‘Carbon Majors’, i.e., large fossil fuel companies.

‘Non-strategic’ climate change related disputes, where the parties bringing the case aim at satisfying individual concerns¹⁵.

‘Strategic’ climate change related disputes can be further subdivided into:

‘In favour of regulation’ or ‘pro-regulation’, where the parties bringing the case aim to enhance climate change mitigation and adaptation measures.

‘Against regulation’ or ‘anti-regulation’, where the parties bringing the case oppose to climate change mitigation and adaptation measures.¹⁶ These also include the so-called ‘Strategic Lawsuits Against Public Participation’ (SLAPPs), namely, civil complaints or counterclaims filed by businesses, government bodies or elected officials against individuals or organisations opposing them on climate change issues, often based on defamation law as well as privacy, confidentiality and data protection rules.¹⁷

2.2.2. *Special categories*

According to their legal basis, climate change related disputes can be divided into the following categories:

‘Climate rights’ disputes, where the parties bringing the case assert that insufficient action to mitigate climate change violates their international and constitutional rights to life, health, food, water, liberty, family life etc.

‘Domestic enforcement’ disputes, where parties bring a case against states, public entities or private entities, including ‘Carbon Majors’, to force them meet set climate change goals and commitments.

‘Failure to adapt’ and ‘impacts of adaptation’ disputes, where parties either bring a case against states, public entities or private entities, including ‘Carbon Majors’, to force them to take the steps necessary to adapt to climate change severe effects, such as extreme weather events, or to request com-

¹⁵ Peel, J., Osofsky, H., *Climate Change Litigation*, Annual Review of Law and Social Science, 16, 2020, pp. 21 et seq.

¹⁶ Savaresi, A., Setzer, J., *Mapping the Whole of the Moon: An Analysis of the Role of Human Rights in Climate Litigation*, 2021. Retrieved May 20, 2024, from <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3787963>.

¹⁷ See in this respect Directive (EU) 2024/1069 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 April 2024 on protecting persons who engage in public participation from manifestly unfounded claims or abusive court proceedings (‘Strategic lawsuits against public participation’), OJ L 2024/1069, 16.04.2024.

compensation for adaptation efforts that caused harm to them or their property.

‘Fossil fuels permitting’ disputes, where the parties bringing the case challenge the environmental permitting and review processes that they allege that overlook a project’s climate change implications.

‘Corporate liability and responsibility’ disputes, where the parties bringing the case request compensation for their harm caused by GHG emissions from companies in the atmosphere.

‘Climate disclosures and greenwashing’ disputes, where the parties bringing the case allege that certain corporate statements about climate change are misleading. These cases involve plaintiffs bringing suits claiming that they relied on those statements to make financial decisions, as well as cases brought by governments enforcing securities disclosure and consumer protection laws, and NGOs challenging alleged ‘greenwashing’ campaigns.¹⁸

‘Investor-state’ disputes, i.e., disputes arising pursuant to bilateral or multilateral investor-state treaties pertaining claims brought by foreign investors for breach of investment protections, such as the fair and equitable treatment standard.¹⁹

‘Contractual’ disputes, i.e., disputes arising from commercial contracts. These may be further subdivided into: i) disputes arising from adaptation, transition or mitigation contracts which directly relate to the UNFCCC and pertain to transitions to new systems to adapt to or to mitigate the effects of climate change, and ii) disputes arising from contracts not related to adaptation, mitigation and transition (e.g., a contractor in charge of construction of a new deep-water harbour disagrees with the owner of the harbour over whether increased salinity of fresh water sources was induced by rising sea-levels, owing to climate change, albeit that other contributing factors may exist).²⁰ This category may include construction disputes relating to delays or breaches, contractual disputes between shareholders involved in the development of RES projects, disputes arising from contracts in the framework of Voluntary Carbon Markets etc.

‘Inter-state’ disputes, i.e., climate change related disputes between states, arising from international treaties (being the less frequent category of disputes in this field).

¹⁸ Categories under a) to f) are described by UNEP, *op.cit.*, pp. 13 et seq.

¹⁹ See Restrepo Rodríguez, T., *Investment Treaty Law and Climate Change*, Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland AG, 2022, *passim*.

²⁰ Category under h) is described in the ICC Commission on Arbitration and ADR, *op.cit.*, pp. 8 et seq.

2.3. The interplay between EU PIL and climate change related disputes

A large number of remedies are addressed against states. Such cases include – among others – The Hague District Court (*Rechtbank Den Haag*) judgment of 24 June 2015 in *Urgenda Foundation et al. v State of the Netherlands* and the German Federal Constitutional Court (Bundesverfassungsgericht) judgment of 29 April 2021 in *Neubauer et al. v Germany*²¹. In the first case, the Hague District Court accepted Urgenda's arguments, finding that the Government's existing pledge to reduce emissions by 17% by 2020 was insufficient to protect the lives of Dutch citizens. The judgment of the Hague District Court was appealed, but on 9 October 2018 the Hague Court of Appeal (*Gerechtshof Den Haag*) dismissed the appeal and upheld the judgment of the Hague District Court, confirming that the Government owed its citizens a duty of care to protect their rights to private and family life, in accordance with Articles 2 and 8 ECHR. The judgment of the Hague Court of Appeal was challenged before the Supreme Court of the Netherlands (*Hoge Raad*), which eventually, on 20 December 2019, upheld the judgment of the Hague Court of Appeal. In the second case, the German Federal Constitutional Court upheld a claim by young plaintiffs challenging the constitutionality of certain provisions of the German Climate Protection Law (*Bundes-Klimaschutzgesetz*) on constitutional and human rights grounds. More recently, on 9 April 2024, in the landmark case *Verein KlimaSeniorinnen Schweiz et al. v Switzerland*,²² the ECtHR ruled that Switzerland is violating the human rights of the older women because the state is not taking the necessary steps to combat global warming. Specifically, the ECtHR found a violation of Article 8 ECHR safeguarding the right to private and family life, this being the first climate change litigation case in which an international court rules that state inaction violates human rights.

On the other hand, an augmented number of remedies are brought before national civil courts and are addressed against companies causing environmental damage due to GHG emissions, including insurance companies. Such companies operate worldwide, affecting various locations at the same time. They are involved in industries such as energy, resource extraction, manufacturing, and transportation, all of which have a notable impact on the environment.

²¹ Both retrieved on 20 May 2024 from <https://climatecasechart.com>.

²² ECtHR Grand Chamber, *Verein KlimaSeniorinnen Schweiz and others v Switzerland*, 9 April 2024. Retrieved 20 May 2024 from <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng/#%22itemid%22:%22001-233206%22>].

Such cases can cross into different legal jurisdictions and involve numerous parties and legal systems. They include – among others – the District Court Essen (*Essen Landesgericht*) judgment of 15 December 2016 in Luciano Lliuya v RWE AG and the Hague District Court (*Rechtbank Den Haag*) judgment of 26 May 2021 in Milieudefensie et al. v Royal DutchShell plc.²³ In the first case, Lliuya, a Peruvian farmer, claimed against RWE, Germany's largest electric company, that it knowingly contributed to climate damage by emitting GHG, and was partly responsible for melting mountain glaciers near his town. The District Court Essen dismissed Lliuya's claim stating that it could not provide effective redress, because Lliuya's situation would be the same even if RWE stopped emitting and there was no 'linear causal chain' within the complex causal relationship between particular emissions and climate change impacts. The Higher Regional Court of Hamm (*Oberlandesgericht Hamm*), on 30 November 2017, recognised the complaint as well-pleaded and admissible, allowing the case to move into the evidentiary phase on whether Lliuya's home is threatened by floods or mudslides and how RWE contributed. The case is still pending. In the second case, the Hague District Court in its judgment of 26 May 2021 found that Shell owed a duty of care to the plaintiffs to reduce emissions from the operation of its entire energy portfolio by 45% by 2030 relative to 2019 emission levels. The case represents a global first, with the court taking the unprecedented step of holding a company legally responsible for its individual contribution to global GHG emissions. Despite filing an appeal against the Hague District Court judgment, Shell has nonetheless announced its intention to increase the speed of its planned transition in line with the judgment.²⁴

At EU level, EU PIL has a crucial role to play in resolving environmental disputes that extend beyond national geographic boundaries, by providing important legal tools for determining the jurisdiction, applicable laws, as well as, at a later stage, the recognition and enforcement of court decisions. The international element required to trigger the application of the EU PIL system can generally exist in a case when either claimants or defendants are from different jurisdictions, or various geographical locations are involved in the litigation²⁵. Remarkably, in the *Milieudefensie et al. v Royal Dutch Shell plc.* case – where a Dutch NGO representing Dutch citizens sued Shell, a company based in the Netherlands at that time – the Hague District Court applied

²³ Both retrieved on 20 May 2024 from <https://climatecasechart.com>.

²⁴ Information retrieved on 20 May 2024 from <https://www.shell.com/media/speeches-and-articles/articles-by-date/the-spirit-of-shell-will-rise-to-the-challenge.html>.

²⁵ Van Calster, G., *Climate change litigation and private international law*, Lex&Forum, 3, 2023, pp. 588-589.

Rome II Regulation²⁶ on the law applicable law to non-contractual obligations, considering the global nature of the GHG emissions involved as reason enough to apply the Rome II Regulation, without needing further detailed considerations. This shows that referral to EU PIL rules can be made in any case of climate change litigation, given the international dimension of the subject matter of the dispute, namely, the global character of the GHG emissions.

3. EU PIL rules applicable to climate change litigation

The following two sub-chapters examine the EU PIL rules that can apply to climate change litigation, and in particular the respective rules on jurisdiction (3.1.) and applicable law (3.2.), aiming at highlighting their fragmented and complex nature, which allows both forum shopping and qualification shopping practices in this field.

3.1. EU PIL rules on jurisdiction

As per the internationally established legal principle, the place of domicile or habitual residence of the defendant represents the primary head of jurisdiction. This principle is embodied in Article 4(1) of Brussels *Ibis* Regulation.²⁷ For this purpose, it is essential to note that a company's domicile is determined by its statutory seat, its central administration, or its principal place of business, as stated in Article 63(1) of Brussels *I bis* Regulation.

Thus, if the company or parent company of a group is domiciled in a country with strict environmental regulations (like the EU aims to have), there would be a strong motivation to file lawsuits in those courts despite the expenses involved. In general, climate change lawsuits against EU companies will target the parent company liable for its GHG emissions reduction policy. However, under the general domestic law of torts, it is possible that not every jurisdiction recognises a breach of a duty of care imposed on the parent company. A lawsuit filed before the courts of the domicile of the parent company might thus fail on the merits if, under the relevant applicable law, civil liability is limited to the GHG emissions of subsidiaries abroad.²⁸

²⁶ Regulation (EC) No 864/2007 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 July 2007 on the law applicable to non-contractual obligations (Rome II), OJ L 199, 31.07.2007, pp. 40-49.

²⁷ Regulation (EU) No 1215/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2012 on jurisdiction and the recognition and enforcement of judgments in civil and commercial matters (recast), OJ L 351, 20.12.2012, pp. 1-32

²⁸ Prévost, E., *Achieving Climate Change Justice: Some Private International Law Issues*, 2023, p. 17. Retrieved May 20, 2024, from SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4450102> or <http://>

Additionally, beyond the fact that the main defendant (i.e., the parent company) can be sued at its place of domicile, other subsidiaries of the same group or counterparties involved in the emissions reduction plan and subsequently in the realisation of the alleged damage can be attracted to the same forum and in the same proceedings by virtue of the co-defendant theory. Article 8(1) of Brussels *Ibis* Regulation provides, for instance, that a person domiciled in the EU may be brought before the courts of another EU Member State where a co-defendant is domiciled if “the claims are so closely connected that it is expedient to hear and determine them together to avoid the risk of irreconcilable judgments resulting from separate proceedings”.²⁹

The tortious nature of emission reduction obligations does not prevent the claimant from suing before the courts where the harmful event took place or is expected to occur, as allowed by Article 7(2) of Brussels *Ibis* Regulation. This gives the claimant the option to sue before the courts of either the place where the damage occurred or may occur, or the place of the event giving rise to the damage.³⁰ Any claimant in any jurisdiction could indeed allege that it suffered some kind of damage at its place of domicile or habitual residence and seize the competent courts of that place.

It is evident that there are many potential forums that the claimant may choose from. Certain jurisdictions may appear more attractive for pursuing climate change cases than others, due to their favourable legal approach towards the claimants and their claims from the point of view of substantive law. Issues such as financing opportunities, including third-party funding, and the availability of cost orders may also constitute critical elements in the context of forum shopping for climate change litigation.³¹ So far, the claimants’ strategy in the EU appears to be focussed on suing Carbon Majors in their home country under the *lex fori*. For example, in the *Milieudefensie et al. v Royal DutchShell plc.* case the lawsuit against Shell was brought in The Hague and based on Dutch law. Likewise, in the *Luciano Lliuya v RWE AG* case the lawsuit was brought at the place of the registered office of the defendant RWE in Germany, with German law applicable, although it concerned imminent damage in Peru.³²

dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4450102.

²⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 17.

³⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 18.

³¹ Van Calster, G., *Climate justice litigation and private international law*, Lex&Forum, 3, 2023, pp. 585-586.

³² Komnios, K., *The “climate trial”: Procedural legal issues*, Lex&Forum, 3, 2023, p. 631 [in Greek].

On the other hand, it should be borne in mind that, based on the *forum non conveniens*-like doctrine outlined in Articles 33-34 of Brussels Ibis Regulation, defendants in an EU court may resist jurisdiction of such court if a case is pending elsewhere. This may encourage knowledgeable corporate defendants to strategically seize a court in ‘friendly’ jurisdictions outside the EU, so that they can avoid a subsequent claim that will be brought against them, and this court would proclaim that they are not liable for whatever environmental or climate damage might have occurred.³³

3.2. EU PIL rules on applicable law

Provided that the case is brought before a court within the EU, as described above, Rome II Regulation shall apply to tort events giving rise to damage which occur after 11 January 2009 – the events being relevant, not the damage.

Article 3 of Rome II Regulation confirms the universal character of its provisions, namely that the Rome II Regulation applies regardless of whether it leads to the law of a non-Member State being applicable. Article 4(1) of Rome II Regulation introduces a general PIL rule, based on which the law of the country where the damage occurs (*lex loci damni*) shall be applicable, irrespective of the country in which the event giving rise to the damage occurred and irrespective of the country or countries in which the indirect consequences of that event occur. Article 4(2) of Rome II Regulation introduces an exception to this rule in case both the claimant and the defendant have their habitual residence in the same country at the time when the damage occurs; in such case, the law of that country shall apply. According to the general escape clause of Article 4(3) of Rome II Regulation, when it is clear from the circumstances of the case that it is manifestly more closely connected with a country other than the one indicated by the above two provisions, the law of that country shall apply instead.³⁴

Rome II Regulation includes specific rules for specific torts, such as product liability, unfair competition and acts restricting free competition, environmental damage, infringement of intellectual property rights, industrial action, as well as the three specific categories of *negotiorum gestio*, unjust enrichment and *culpa in contrahendo*, which relate to a contract.

According to Article 7 of Rome II Regulation, the law applicable to a non-contractual obligation arising out of environmental damage or damage

³³ Van Calster (2023), *op.cit.*, p. 589.

³⁴ Van Calster, G., *European Private International Law (4th ed.)*, Oxford et al.: Hart, 2024, pp. 325 et seq.

sustained by persons or property as a result of such damage shall be the law determined pursuant to Article 4(1) of Rome II Regulation, i.e., the law of the country where the damage occurs (*lex loci damni*) – irrespective of the country where the event giving rise to the damage occurred and irrespective of the country or countries where the indirect consequences of that event occur – unless the party seeking compensation for damage chooses to base its claim on the law of the country where the event giving rise to the damage occurred (*lex loci delicti commissi*).

Recitals 24-25 relate to Article 7 of Rome II Regulation. According to them, ‘environmental damage’ should be understood as meaning adverse change in a natural resource, such as water, land or air, impairment of a function performed by that resource for the benefit of another natural resource or the public, or impairment of the variability among living organisms. Moreover, regarding environmental damage, Article 174 of the Treaty, which provides that there should be a high level of protection based on the precautionary principle and the principle that preventive actions should be taken, the principle of priority for corrective action at source and the principle that the polluter pays, fully justifies the use of the principle of discriminating in favour of the person sustaining the damage. The question of when the person seeking compensation can make the choice of the law applicable should be determined in accordance with the law of the Member State in which the court is seated. The choice allowed by Article 7 of Rome II Regulation clearly provides a favourable option for claimants, including those from third countries, who can select the law of the place of central administration of the parent company as *lex loci delicti commissi*. This approach was used by the Hague District Court in the *Milieudefensie et al. v Royal Dutch Shell plc* case.³⁵

At this point, the potential impact of Article 17 of Rome II Regulation should be also taken into account. According to this, in assessing the conduct of the person claimed to be liable, account shall be taken, as a matter of fact and in so far as is appropriate, of the rules of safety and conduct which were in force at the place and time of the event giving rise to the liability.³⁶ Such

³⁵ Van Calster, G., *Lexecologia. On applicable law for environmental pollution (Article 7 Rome II), a pinnacle of business and human rights as well as climate change litigation*, IPRax, 2022, pp. 447 et seq.

³⁶ Cf. European Parliament legislative resolution of 24 April 2024 on the proposal for a directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence and amending Directive (EU) 2019/1937 (COM(2022)0071 – C9-0050/2022 – 2022/0051(COD)). Retrieved May 20, 2024, from https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-9-2024-0329_EN.html. Based on the provisions of the CSDDD, Member States should mandatorily implement corporate due diligence requirements in supply chains.

rules play a crucial role in judging the behaviour of the person liable, and their importance will depend on the specific conduct and the other surrounding circumstances, as well as the legal framework governing the non-contractual obligation in question.³⁷ If liability under the applicable law is strict, the conduct of the person liable may not fall to be assessed at all.

This 'conduct and safety rules' provision bears specific relevance in the context of environmental damage. However, it is unclear whether this could cover a 'permit defence' rule which Member States may adopt under the Environmental Liability Directive (EDL),³⁸ raising concerns about the application of foreign public law by courts in different jurisdictions. According to Article 8(4)(a) EDL, the Member States may allow the operator not to bear the cost of remedial actions taken pursuant to its provisions where such operator demonstrates that it was not at fault or negligent and that the environmental damage was caused by an emission or event expressly authorised by, and fully in accordance with the conditions of, an authorisation conferred by or given under applicable national laws and regulations which implement those legislative measures adopted by the EU specified in Annex III of the EDL, as applied at the date of the emission or event. It is argued that an environmental permit, as a much more extensive instrument than merely containing 'rules of safety and conduct', does not fall within the scope of Article 17 of Rome II Regulation, meaning that permits of the *lex loci delicti commissi* should not have any impact if the applicable law is the *lex loci damni*. Namely, it is debated whether environmental laws, even when they are part of the EU legislation, can be viewed as foreign public law and therefore may not be enforceable in a different jurisdiction.³⁹

It is crucial to keep in mind that the Rome II Regulation provisions are not the only that may apply in climate change related disputes. In many cases, Rome I Regulation⁴⁰ on the law applicable to contractual obligations

³⁷ Dickinson, A., *The Rome II Regulation: The Law Applicable to Non-Contractual Obligations*, OUP: Oxford, 2008, p. 641.

³⁸ Directive 2004/35/CE of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 April 2004 on environmental liability with regard to the prevention and remedying of environmental damage, OJ L 143 30.4.2004, pp. 56-75.

³⁹ See in this respect Van Calster (2023), op.cit., p. 591; idem. (2022), op. cit., pp. 447 et seq. See also Hübner, L., *Climate Change Litigation an der Schnittstelle von öffentlichem Recht und Privatrecht – Die ausländische Anlagengenehmigung*, IPRax, 2022, p. 223; Álvarez-Armas, E., *Le contentieux international privé en matière de changement climatique à l'épreuve de l'article 17 du règlement Rome II : enjeux et perspectives*, RDIA, 3, 2020, pp. 115 et seq.

⁴⁰ Regulation (EC) No 593/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 June 2008 on the law applicable to contractual obligations (Rome I), OJ L 177, 4.7.2008, pp. 6-16.

could also be applicable, especially in matters concerning insurance. Thus, in the particular cases the *lex contractus* may be a relevant factor, also for limitations of liability. Additionally, when looking at Rome II Regulation, one should not solely concentrate on Article 7 thereof. There may be a more suitable legal option for a claimant that is hidden under a different qualification, such as unfair competition, product liability etc. For example, unjust enrichment or unfair competition areas may also be important avenues for climate change lawsuits. A practical approach in these situations is known as ‘reverse engineering’, where one first selects the most advantageous law for the claim and then shapes the claim strategically to match that chosen legal provision.⁴¹

4. Conclusion

The above analysis brought attention to the fragmentation and complexity of the current EU PIL framework in relation to the particular case of climate change related claims. Such framework at the moment promotes to a large extent both forum shopping and qualification shopping practices, especially among sophisticated claimants who are skilled in understanding the intricacies of the EU PIL system and know how to manipulate such system for their advantage. This can result in legal uncertainty and potential abuse of the particular rights by the claimants. Therefore, there is a question of whether a new uniform EU PIL framework is necessary to specifically address climate change cases.

Summary

Climate change has progressively emerged as a critical global concern, involving various sectors and stakeholders. Internationally, both soft law guiding principles and hard law legislative instruments address the phenomenon, imposing obligations on states and entities, while impacting commercial contracts across various industries. This leads to potential disputes regarding environmental laws or contractual violations related to climate issues.

The paper first discusses the typology of disputes related to climate change, including the prerequisites for applying the EU PIL. In *Milieudefensie et al. v Royal DutchShell plc.*, the Hague District Court applied Rome II Regulation considering that the global nature of the GHG emissions involved as reason enough to apply the Rome II, without further considerations.

⁴¹ Van Calster (2023), *op.cit.*, p. 590.

Subsequently, the paper provides an overview the EU PIL rules regarding jurisdiction and applicable law in this context. According to Brussels *Ibis*, the place of domicile or habitual residence of the defendant represents the primary head of jurisdiction. The tortious nature of emission reduction obligations does not prevent the claimant from suing before the courts where the harmful event took place or is expected to occur, offering the option to sue before the courts of either the place where the damage occurred or may occur, or the place of the event giving rise to the damage. Moreover, various provisions of Rome II, as well as Rome I, may be applicable to a particular case depending on the qualification of the obligation in question, resulting in the potential application of different substantive laws accordingly.

The analysis brings attention to the fragmentation and complexity of the current EU PIL framework in relation to climate change litigation, which promotes both forum shopping and qualification shopping practices. Therefore, there is a question of whether a new uniform EU PIL framework is necessary to specifically address climate change cases.

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Abbreviations

CSDDD = Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive

COP = Conference of the Parties to the UNFCCC

CO₂ = Carbon dioxide

ECHR = European Convention on Human Rights

ECtHR = European Court of Human Rights

EDL = Environmental Liability Directive

GHG = Greenhouse gas

GSIA = Global Sustainable Investment Alliance

ICC = International Chamber of Commerce

IPCC = Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

NGO = Non-Governmental Organisation

PIL = Private International Law

SLAPP = Strategic Lawsuit Against Public Participation

UN = United Nations

UNCITRAL = United Nations Commission on International Trade Law

UNEP = United Nations Environment Programme

UNFCCC = United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change